

Social Marketing and Nonprofit Organizations

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Abstract—Today the social marketing was constituted as a tool of significant value in what he refers to the promotion of changes of behaviors, attitudes end practices. With the objective of analyzing the benefits that the social marketing can bring for the organizations that use it the research was of the exploratory and descriptive. In the present study the comparative method was used, through a qualitative approach, to analyze the activities developed by three institutions: the Recovery Center Rosa de Saron, the House of Recovery for addicts and Teen Challenge Institute Children's Cancer of the Wasteland (ICIA), kindred of pointing out the benefits of the social marketing in organizations that don't seek the profit.

Keywords—Social marketing, organizations of the third section, social changes

I. INTRODUCTION

TODAY, marketing deals, along with finance, personnel management and operations, a place of prominence in business administration. However, for many organizations, marketing is restricted to strategies that sometimes attach themselves only to issues of communication for advertising and publicity. According to the reference [1], the attributions of different meanings to marketing generate conceptual decrease and inadvertent use of a term to denote different practices.

Starting in 1969, Philip Kotler, Sidney Levy, William Lazer, among other authors cited by the reference [2], begin to emphasize the social dimensions of marketing. The reference [3] emphasizes that the concept of social marketing is an orientation to consumer needs, supported by integrated marketing, aiming at generating consumer satisfaction and welfare in the long term, as a means to achieve organizational goals. In 1978, Kotler published the book "Marketing for Non-profit Organizations" in Brazil, in which emphasizes the application of marketing in the social area. There was thus an evolution of the concept of marketing, which was originally developed for production, then to sales and then to an integrated sense [3].

Being one of the marketing derivations, social marketing to Kotler and Zaltman, according the reference [4] was

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established as a tool of significant value when it comes to promoting change behaviors, attitudes and practices.

Considering then the importance of using social marketing as an effective and promoter tool of the aforementioned changes, and difficulties imposed by the market, raises the following question: organizations that are non-profit and use social marketing strategies perform better in achieving their goals than those who do not use such strategies?

The Non-Governmental Organizations - NGOs are social agents with a high specific weight, both in solving the problems of disadvantaged communities as the work of raising and educating the public [5].

The use of social marketing in such organizations, with its strategy to changes the behavior of society, can help them to achieve their goals.

This study aims to examine the benefits that social marketing can bring to organizations that use and no use of it can lead to greater difficulty in achieving the goals of nonprofit organizations, so that you can identify the consequences arising from the use or non-use of social marketing.

The goal of this research will be achieved by examining the activities of non-profit organizations located in the city of Caruaru-PE, which were: the Recovery Center Rosa de Saron, the House of Recovery for addicts and Teen Challenge Institute Children's Cancer of the Wasteland (ICIA), seeking to understand the activities undertaken by such organizations, examining how these institutions use social marketing strategies and highlighting its benefits in such organizations.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

A. Third Section Organizations

The third sector organizations, through activities that promote social welfare and lacking-profit, aim at the promotion of actions that the public benefit [6]-[7]-[8].

The references [9] and [10] argue that among the difficulties of managing nonprofit organizations, one of the biggest challenges is getting the money due to the character of their actions (social promotion), rather than the financial-economic model pursued by the funding corporations.

The product is the idea, knowledge, belief, attitude, habit or behavior that one wishes to convey to the target segments. So there are three forms of social product: (I) social idea that is assumed as belief, attitude or value, (II) social practice and (III) tangible object [11].

Among the challenges remaining to the third sector, The references [12] argues for the existence of four: a) challenge

the legitimacy - that it is the quest for distinction of the third sector, b) Challenge efficiency - the sector needs to demonstrate ability and competence; c) Challenge of Sustainability - this is the difficulty of subsistence both financial and the number of individuals committed to social causes; d) Challenge of collaboration - regarding the need for participation private sector, state and other entities of the third sector, due to lack of resources have become competitive with each other.

Facing the challenges seen so far, much can be seen on the difficulties encountered by nonprofit organizations to keep active in the marketplace. Soon, the reference [13] agrees that organizations that develop social projects must rely on social marketing to plan their social campaigns, culminating in the maintenance and expansion of their market niche.

B. Social Marketing

The reference [3] defines social marketing as the design, implementation and control programs that seek to increase the acceptance of an idea in a focus group. Use the concepts of market segmentation, consumer research, the configuration of ideas, communications, facilitation of incentives and exchange theory in order to maximize the reaction of the target group.

Social marketing is conceptualized by the reference [14] as an exchange of physical values, economic, social, moral or political factors that is used to sell ideas or purposes that provide welfare to the community.

The reference [11] brings yet another definition, social marketing is a strategy for changing behavior. It combines the best elements of traditional approaches to social change in an integrated scheme for planning and action and takes advantage of advances in communications technology and marketing capacity.

In other settings, the reference [4] argues that social marketing is a public point of view of consumers, while the reference [15] proposes the following definition, social marketing is a tool democratic and efficient system that applies the principles and tools of marketing to create and grant a greater social value to the proposal, finding again the consumer through interactive dialogue, creating conditions for the build process of reflection, participation and social change.

C. Purpose of Activity and Social Marketing

The real social marketing operates primarily on communication with employees and their families, with actions that aim to increase its proven social welfare and community. These actions ensure medium and long term sustainability, citizenship, solidarity and social cohesion [16].

Choosing the right goal or objective for a social marketing program is essential. The social marketing campaigns may be aimed at changing the cognitions, values, actions or behaviors. The real success of social marketing program should be evaluated in terms of the proposed objectives [17].

The organization sponsoring the social marketing is targeting the goals of social change, the understanding that they contribute to the public interest. "It will depend on how easy or difficult it is social change". Without social marketing, it might happen that the desired social change has only ten

percent chance of being achieved, the best plan for social marketing can increase this probability to fifteen percent [3].

D. Social Change

Results of the application of social marketing, in turn, seek to achieve four types of social change. The first is cognitive in nature, when campaigns are established through public information programs and public education. Examples of these are: campaigns to explain the nutritional value of different foods; campaigns to draw attention to social problems like poverty, intolerance or pollution, among others [3].

According the same reference the second is the change of action. Regarding the causes of cognitive change presents the greatest difficulties being taken at the end, because the target market has to learn something different from their normal repertoire and perform a specific action based on what was learned. The shift action is present when they are promoted campaigns to influence people to attend a mass immunization, campaigns to attract women over forty years to conduct examinations for cancer prevention, campaigns to raise money for charitable purposes; campaigns to attract donors blood or organ donation.

Every action involves a cost to the person, factors such as time, distance, costs, or even inertia (the fruit of conformism) can make it difficult to achieve them. Another class, which takes into account the individual welfare, it aims to induce or help people to change behavior. The behavior of people is known to be harmful to health, but the person is not able or at least is not willing to change their behavior. These causes include efforts to reduce smoking addiction, efforts to discourage alcohol consumption, efforts to discourage the use of narcotics [18].

Behavior change is more difficult to achieve. Often the person is aware that their consumption habits are harmful to your health and still cannot take a single action to end the temptations to which it is subject. Thus the greatest difficulty will help her change the routine behavior that is rooted in their systems [3].

The last change to be considered in marketing efforts to understand social change ideas that people have about abortion, efforts to increase participation and respect for women's work, efforts towards the preservation of public goods, and other causes including the most difficult to implemented, it is the change in value. These changes clash with the sense of identity and well-being of an individual who is crystallized in its core values, which guide their perceptions and social choices, moral and intellectual [3].

E. Use of Social Marketing

According to the reference [16], there are several ways to use social marketing: a) Marketing sponsorship of philanthropy: based on the donation made by the company to an entity that will benefit; b) social marketing campaigns: means to convey messages of public interest through product packaging; c) Marketing sponsorship of social programs: sponsorship may be others, with companies working in partnership with governments in financing their social actions.

There are two types of sponsorship of social projects: the first case is to sponsor social projects of others, where we have companies that work closely with governments in financing their social actions. The second case is to sponsor its own social projects, in which "those companies that have, through their social institutions and foundations, create their own designs and implement their own resources"; d) Marketing of relationship-based social action : Uses the company's sales personnel to steer clients as users of social services; e) social marketing to promote product and brand the company uses the name of an entity or a campaign logo, adding value to your business and generating increased sales.

One must then understand social marketing, if properly monitored and evaluated its consequences, as a tool made available to all staff concerned with the necessary changes in the social fabric, so that in a democratic society, the intentions of Social marketing is acceptable in terms of ethics and social issues. So, not only with the communication of persuasive that these people will adopt and comply with safety standards. The perfect formation of an opinion and not a feeling, that will achieve the result of change [18].

Social marketing has much to contribute to the third sector, with its strategies of behavior change in society, however, institutions need to see this need [19].

Unlike the institutions that do not have a marketing strategy in organizational structure, they have, get more ideas and go further, achieving behavior change in society and therefore more engagement of volunteers in contributing to the social cause.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Study Design

The comparative method is used in this study. This method seeks to highlight similarities and differences among people, patterns and phenomena [20]. This method is applied in several areas of science, especially in the social sciences. Its use is due to the possibility offered by the study of working with large human groups in different population universes and even, sometimes, distanced by geographical space [21].

Aiming to analyze the benefits that social marketing can bring to organizations that use and whether non-use may lead to greater difficulty in achieving its goals, the research is exploratory and descriptive.

The exploratory research are developed in order to provide overview of rough type about a particular fact. By its nature the survey, do not involve assumptions that, however, may arise during or after the search [20]. The descriptive characteristics in turn exposes a certain population or a particular phenomenon but has no commitment to explain the phenomena it describes, although as the basis for such an explanation.

This study has a qualitative approach. Sometimes referred to as naturalistic research, phenomenological, interpretive or ethnographic, it is a kind of "umbrella", which includes a variety of techniques of non-quantitative studies [22].

The qualitative approach, in general, is used mainly to discover and refine the research questions. The emphasis of

this approach is not to measure the variables involved in the phenomenon, but to understand it [22].

The activities developed in some non-profit organizations using social marketing will be thereby analyzed in order to highlight the benefits of such use.

B. Data Collection

The way in which data were collected was through the application of in-depth interviews with members of organizations. This interview technique is fundamental to qualitative research and is regarded as the basic method of social sciences. The interviews were semi-structured by using open questions. This type of question gives the condition researched talk spontaneously about what is being asked, the answers are free, resolution, without limitations and with its own language [21]. Thus, the researcher is not predetermining their view through prior selection of categories of issues, such as who uses a quantitative method [23].

C. Data Analysis

The interviews were transcribed and extracted the most important parts. To analyze the texts that were raised by these interviews were used discourse analysis and content analysis [24].

The discourse analysis, focuses on the language as used in social texts, written or spoken, including, therefore, material from interviews and open responses to questionnaires, group discussions and documents. Content analysis, in turn, uses a series of procedures to raise valid inferences from text. The method seeks to classify words, phrases or even paragraphs in content categories [25].

In the selection of respondents are considered the following factors: the level of information (aiming to acquire the most information possible about the organization) and the role (understanding that this factor influences with regard to a more comprehensive knowledge about organizational activities). Were interviewed the director - and founder of Rosa de Saron, ICIA's Executive Manager and Secretary of Teen Challenge - stressing that it was holding an extensive knowledge about the organization under study, also collaborating in the administration of NGOs.

The data were subjected to content analysis, being defined as units of analysis sentences and paragraphs. Drawing on the open grill, according Vergara (2005), consists in identifying the categories of analysis that arise while the researcher, we defined four categories for analysis: (I) Definition of objectives, (II) Major problems; (III) Government and Second Sector, and (IV) Application of Social Marketing. Branching out in the last three subcategories: (a) Campaigns; (b) Social changes; and (c) Forms of use.

Interviews lasted between 06 and 32 minutes, being held between 25/06/2010 and 28/06/2010, resulting in just over 30 minutes of recordings and seven transcribed pages. The interview process began with a screenplay with questions based on the references. During the interviews, the initial script was being slightly changed, this flexibility allows the

interviewer to phrase the question so that the informant can understand it more easily [26].

IV. PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

A. Goal Settings

To promote actions aimed at public benefit, providing some kind of service to society matches the goal of not for profit organizations [27].

"The objectives are: to provide treatment, consultation, pre - cancer diagnosis to children and adolescents in the region, okay. At the moment we're with these consultations, we are only with these queries. Also, social support, which is seen in families of social, psychological, okay. Today our day-to-day it is. It is the care, diagnosis, monitoring social and psychological." (Executive Manager of ICIA)

"The goal of Rose of Sharon is to restore lives. It is ... we work with an audience that is complicated, because women are far more complicated than man, eh! And it's more expensive. [...] We work with adolescents and adults. [...]" (Founder of the Center for Recovery Rosa de Saron)

"The objective of the institution is willing to treat the internal reinstate him to society ... largely succeeds, others quit." (Secretary of Recovery House Teen Challenge)

Each organization confirms, through its objectives, its societal responsibility.

B. Majors Problems

The sustainability of nonprofit organizations, greatly differ from organizations in the second sector, because their product as claimed, is the idea or behavior to the desired target audience [10]. Faced with this fact, not for profit organizations that are struggling.

"... I confess that the biggest difficulty is the accessibility of the population the institution. I know the demand is high, we attend many children, there is still much ignorance of the population to know the institution, to know how we work, we support that provides free people." (Executive Manager of ICIA)

"... even greater difficulty is the lack of people to help. Because this process of adaptation that the Rose of Sharon's passing, we are being penalized because they have 13 girls here that they have been through recovery today they want to stay at home as a worker, such as cooperating, and we ta dress up as being exploitative, it alienates those girls for them helping us stay here, and it is not true, then the biggest difficulty is that [...]" (Founder of Recovery Center Rosa de Saron)

"[...] Thus, the structure of the house has a lot to do, a financial hardship because the cost of a domestic same, only

food, water we spend is \$ 600.00. What telemarketing copper, copper to help the population, it is practically feeding them. The rest we'll keep trying and it will turning a snowball. Ends, so we cannot hire more staff, so we can have a better structure to receive, when it reaches a certain amount of internal, we've got to stop receiving because it has enough staff to meet [...]." (Secretary of Recovery House Teen Challenge)

Among the four objectives set out by the reference [12], demonstrate the challenge of sustainability, because the lack of resources that ends up hurting the progress of the organization, but also the challenge of collaboration, which impairs organizational development due to a number lack of contributors, volunteers.

C. According to Government and Industry

Two of the three organizations have a lack concerning the assistance by the State Government as well as the Second Sector, with greater emphasis on addressing the challenge of collaboration.

"... only the population that has sustained." (Executive Manager of ICIA).

"It's just the population that remains. [...] Both the government makes the project that will do a clinic and so far nothing comes out. And many people also can not afford to bear the expense of a child, then the child ends up getting lost in that world because they will have no solution for him." (Secretary of Recovery House Teen Challenge)

Rosa de Saron The organization has support from both the city as entrepreneurs, significant maintenance, generally in the same.

"... Mayor ... Today he helps us with the Literate Brazil program, as well as Pro-Youth, and bread and milk gives it [...] switch-on of the mayor and also with this new challenge, this new construction of the Rose of Sharon ... and he said that the city may need the count, he gave us last paper, sanitation, construction of a square, afforestation, gave them three month paper, and said it would give more: the wall, the construction of the Church ... and the construction of a school. [...] We received help from two businessmen. Your Amaro is the owner of Etigraf. It was he who made this whole project there with the help of a businesswoman who owns Limak, Gorete, who sits on the board [...] And today she is a partner-sponsor ... It also has a dentist who're with me from the beginning that is elicited, it also sits on the board, and is a blessing, is always here with me and ready, only those three. [...]" (Founder of Recovery Center Rosa de Saron)

The help of the second allowed the third sector organization relevant advantages in its development since the Rose of Sharon with better improvement in its structure compared to the other two organizations.

D. Application of Social Marketing (Campaigns)

Two of the organizations presented an evolutionary framework as the campaigns developed.

"Well ... The beginning was that old community social action of some physicians treating, at home, children, the word-of-mouth, then everyone would know, then everyone came in contact. Has thus emerged. Today we have several campaigns, a large weight is the Walk for Life, where people mobilize much of the population walking down the road and promoting the work, what we offer. Also has other I just say that is the Early Diagnosis, okay. Just a publicity campaign for the only such institution. Where radio, newspapers, TV, we're always spreading, some action, like, just now had the feijoada, before then had dinner, so we always use the media to disseminate. We have a very good team of professionals, where they are trained and work out all year." (Executive Manager of ICIA)

"In the beginning was the word-of-mouth it. (Today) ... writing the paper, the newspaper said. We go on the radio and myself is that I seek. When thus has a campaign, as he had now little about child exploitation, they came and they did a story with the girls and then me, that's also a way to spread [...] This week a police officer even came here he said "Jane, we will disclose it, I want you to go in the battalion, I will perform there for you, for they come here and know", have these people coming so, as my friend and also the Official Vanguard also most of the time I'm there I see the difficulty here there'll call board and say 'Oh, that? I'll call the press "... Thank God today we have a press officer [...]" (Founder of Recovery Center Rosa de Saron)

Teen Challenge has had a disability in the course of his twenty years, the lack of financial resources has stalled the development of campaigns.

"... recovered was the first director here, you know, it's José Bartolomeu de Araújo ... he resolved to recover more people were getting stuff ..., getting help from the Church ... he was also a drug user, then he did a lot of talk out his testimony, DVD sales, CD sales, is ... he did much publicity, it was much publicity, because in every state he did talk [...]. Regarding disclosure at the moment we're not on account of financial difficulties already. Because any divulgaçãozinha is expensive ... and this has hampered [...]" (Secretary of Recovery House Teen Challenge)

Organizations conducting campaigns - Children's Cancer Institute of the Wasteland (ICIA) and Rosa de Saron - are more likely to achieve their goals of the organization which does not use such campaigns - Teen Challenge, for these campaigns promote a greater awareness society about their causes, and this reflects positively on the organization.

E. Application of Social Marketing (Social Transformations)

The results of the use of social marketing in the Rose of Sharon and ICIA has focused on two of the four types of social changes mentioned by Fortes (1999): cognitive change and behavior. The company has responded to the causes of these two NGOs in a positive way, then you realize, that social marketing campaigns have been and are being successful because the goals set are being met, and according to the reference [17] success legitimate social marketing needs to be analyzed in terms of ends chosen.

"... when we see who are suffering for want of food, or something, I call the press and say 'look we come here to put the blow the whistle, as they say, and make a call like this for society and this, with this matter being disclosed, there comes the material." (Founder of the Center for Recovery Rosa de Saron)

"It's so much that we started to build the hospital, several blocks, now we have the clinic, which is where the consultation takes place and the social and psychological treatment. That is, the population helps a lot." (Executive Manager of ICIA)

Even without making use of properly planned campaigns, the Teen Challenge promotes an annual event (the celebration of the anniversary of the NGO) that brings together employees and allows the organization to make an appeal to increase the number of volunteers, but also show what is being applied to the contribution of each employee, but the absence of social marketing campaigns contributes to organizational inefficiency, thus hindering the effectiveness of the House.

"So ... we have every year the anniversary of the challenge is a way we found to meet the staff works. A, í here they can see where the money ... is being invested ... there one called ... called relative, called a friend, neighbor, then the contribution increases slightly, there is a loyal and are donating every month and not others [...]" (Secretary of Recovery House Teen Challenge)

F. Application of Social Marketing (Ways to use)

Among the uses of social marketing cited by the reference [14], none of the organizations under study have benefited from some of these forms. It is noteworthy that the Rose of Sharon gets rather a support from both the city and businessmen, however, none of entrepreneurs launched a social marketing campaign tied to the company in order to focus on the cause of the NGO.

V.CONCLUSION

In the analysis of the benefits that social marketing can bring to organizations that are non-profit through understanding of activities of the organizations under study, this research concludes that when used, the social marketing strategies enable a better performance with regard to achievement of organizational objectives.

The absence of aid from both the Second Sector and the Government in two of the three organizations studied is an issue that deserves attention because it is by entities that seek the public good the lack of support from these sectors hinders the satisfactory development of the NGO. Civil society then becomes largely responsible for the sustainability of most non-profit organizations.

It was clearly shown the difficulty that an organization that does not use such strategies is to keep "alive" and active in society. Through this study it was noted that the financial factor corresponds to an influential part in planning social marketing campaigns. Without such a campaign organization loses 'strength', and the same survival becomes more difficult.

The campaigns make viable the company receive a higher amount of information about the organization and therefore about their needs. The Rose of Sharon and ICIA confirm this fact when using the press to promote their causes, and this reflects positively, as the company responds to the call through its contribution, especially civil society.

Thus, to prove the benefits of the social marketing to non-governmental organizations, as well as the consequences and obstacles faced by organizations that do not use – or precariously do – social marketing strategies, stressing the need organizations that are non-profit use of this effective instrument in order to achieve their goals.

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